

Efficient production of tri-acetylated mono-acylated mannosylerythritol lipids by *Sporisorium* sp. aff. *sorghii* SAM20

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Abstract

Aims: The aim of this study was to isolate a novel yeast strain, evaluate biosurfactant production by the strain and characterize the major product. **Methods and Results:** The strain SAM20, isolated from grass, identified as *Sporisorium* sp. aff. *sorghii* based on phylogenetic analyses. The strain produced approximately 32 g l⁻¹ glycolipid biosurfactants from 40 g l⁻¹ soybean oil after 7 days at 28°C. The glycolipids showed a unique pattern of mannosylerythritol lipids (MELs) on thin layer chromatography plate compared to those hitherto reported. Structural characterization of the major product, called GL-A, revealed that it was mainly tri-acetylated mono-acylated MELs (MEL-A2) with C14:0, C16:0, C12:0 or C14:1 as the hydrophobic chain. The critical micelle concentration (CMC), the surface tension at CMC and hydrophilic–lipophilic balance value for GL-A were estimated to be 20 mg l⁻¹, 30.0 mN m⁻¹ and 8.7, respectively.

Conclusions: A MEL-A2 with novel composition and surface activities was efficiently produced from a novel MEL producer. This is the first report on production of MEL-A2 as the major product and from soybean oil. The biosurfactant has potential application as a wetting agent and oil-in-water emulsifier.

Significance and Impact of the Study: Discovery of novel structures and novel strains is valuable for further commercial development and application of MELs. *Sporisorium* sp. aff. *sorghii* SAM20 can be considered as a potential candidate for commercial production of biosurfactants

Keywords: biosurfactant, glycolipid, hydrophilic–lipophilic balance, mannosylerythritol lipid, *Sporisorium* sp. aff. *sorghii*, surface activity.